

CHALLENGES IN GREEN CAMPUS INITIATIVE AMONG COLLEGE TEACHERS
A STUDY OF UGC RECOGNISED EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Global warming has led to catastrophic climate change in almost all part of the world. And the major contributors for this effect are human beings. It becomes the responsibility of the people to reduce CO₂ emission work for the benefit of a healthy plant. As the younger generation is to witness this effect, it becomes the responsibility of the educational institutions to instill green lifestyles among the receptive students by introducing green initiatives among the campus which can definitely help to reduce global warming and temperature. This paper aims at understanding the Challenges in Green Campus initiative and this study was conducted among UGC recognized educational institutions. The methodology adopted for the study was simple random sampling. For this, the faculties of Government, Aided and Autonomous institutions were selected to know their awareness and interest on green campus initiative. Questionnaire were distributed among the teachers for collecting the data. Data was collected from 80 respondents. The objective of the paper was to know the green initiative taken by various colleges, their awareness regarding the concept and also to know the limiting factors that restrict the campus to go green.

KEYWORDS: Green Campus, Green Initiative, Eco – friendly, Bio diversity, Energy efficient

INTRODUCTION

A Green Campus is a place where environmental friendly practices and education combine to promote sustainable and eco-friendly practices in the campus. The green campus concept offers an institution the opportunity to take the lead in redefining its environmental culture and developing new paradigms by creating sustainable solutions to environmental, social and economic needs of the mankind (Nahar2018). The aim of Green Campus should be to develop environmental awareness and it should be the intrinsic part of the life of an institution. It aims at developing responsible attitude to the environment and rewards long term commitment for the improvement of our environment continuously. Green campus status can be achieved by making significant progress in campus community by focusing on water, waste, energy, bio diversity etc. This will definitely help in bring a positive change in the campus, helps students to live life positively. Making the campus green is all about wiping off wasteful inefficiencies by implementing effective recycling program, adopting correct disposal methods and also in the purchase of environment friendly supplies. In order to implement green campus initiatives, Institute has to work out effective time bound strategies. It becomes the responsibility of every campus to take necessary measures to implement all those strategies to make Campus green. It also has its impact on quality of life of stakeholders.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Greening the campus is all about clearing away all wasteful inefficiencies and applying conventional sources of energies for its daily disposal handling, and power need, purchasing of environment friendly or organic supplies and adopting effective recycling or reusing programs. With the growing need for developing green initiative in the campus, the campuses have to make all the necessary efforts to involve faculties, students and other staff members. The faculty, staff and students have to contribute collectively to develop an eco-friendly sustainable campus and disseminate the concept of eco-friendly culture to the nearby community and wherever possible. So there is an urgent need among the stakeholders of every educational institution to understand the awareness of green campus and also the practices to be undertaken to make the campus green in all forms. A paper titled 'Environmental Performance Studies' on educational institutions' presented in the International Journal of Environmental Sciences states that educational campuses consume more natural resources than any small and medium enterprise (SMES). As per the paper a developing university consumes about 8, 00,000 liters of water and uses about 5,333 kilowatt hour of electricity per day for their operations. Green Campus enables the institutes to conserve natural resources, manage waste, optimize energy efficiency and

educate about sustainability and climate change while addressing the well – being of the stakeholders as compared to non – green or conventional institutes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Brundtland Report defined sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (United Nations 1987). It becomes the responsibility of the human race to ensure that the planet will continue to have sufficient water, clean air and other resources for its living systems.

For academic institutions, the Stockholm Declaration of 1972 addressed the Sustainability in Higher Education (SHE). The declaration focused on finding ways in which universities, their leaders, lecturers, researchers, and students can engage their resources in responding to the challenges of balancing between the human quest for economic and technological development with environmental preservation.

Tiyarattanachai & Hollmann (2016) in their study compared perception of stakeholders in Green Campus and Non-Green Campus universities in Thailand regarding stakeholders’ satisfaction on sustainability practices and perceived quality of life at their campuses. The results showed that stakeholders at the studied Green Campus University were more satisfied and had significantly better perceived quality of life compared to stakeholders from the studied Non-Green Campus University. The results suggested that universities should adopt the criteria set in the UI GreenMetric World University Ranking to achieve better sustainability in their campuses and improve quality of life of their stakeholders.

Foo (2013) stated that higher education is a great contributor for society to achieve sustainability. University researchers provided first alarms regarding environmental challenges through their research investigations.

Based on a study in 2013, students perceived green spaces important for the image of the university and as an essential component of the campus environment (Speake et al (2013)

On one point of view, campus expansion has resulted in an increase in the use of motor vehicles and resource consumption (Balsas (2013). Therefore, many universities around the world have attempted to transform their campuses to make them greener. In Malaysia, some efforts were spent to establish a campus greenway network, which provided pleasant condition for walkers, joggers, and cyclists (Foo (2013).

(Hooi, Hassan, & Mat, 2012) seeks to explore emerging themes following the green campus initiative and to validate critical factors for successful green implementation through the means of empirical evidence through both quantitative and qualitative research approach. The study also hopes to develop a “customized” Green University Framework based on localization approach and to explore the readiness of Malaysia Higher Institution to engage and gauge the important of implementing Green University (GU) initiatives at their respective organization.

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Foo (2013) stated that higher education is a great contributor for society to achieve sustainability. Through research inquiry, researchers has pinpointed about the environmental challenges However, it is a high time for the educational institutions to prepare themselves to transform their campus to a green and clean campus. This can be done by making themselves energy efficient, by adopted water conservation, managing waste inside the campus, designing natural lighting and ventilation and depending less on air conditioners etc.

Sanusi and Khelghat-doost (2008) further stated that ‘Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) also enables people to develop the knowledge, value and skills to participate in decisions about the way we do things, individually and collectively, locally and globally, that will improve the quality of life now without damaging the future of the planet. As such, institutions of higher learning will undoubtedly contribute greatly to this process.’ It is clear that the role of higher education institution is crucial in implementing the ESD principles because it is the place to educate young generation who will be leader in the future. The other role of higher education institution is to insert ESD

principles in their strategic management as part of their responsibility to the society and achieve a sustainable recognition.

According to Royet. Al; (2008), there are two main issues in environmental programmes for the Higher Education (HE) which are reducing energy consumption and waste on campuses, and on “greening the curriculum”. One of the best way to reduce the environmental impact is by home-based and distance learning, including e-learning courses which is provided online via internet. The environmental impact become possible to be reduced because distance learning is eliminates or reduces the infrastructure and activities that used in conventional learning.

Narrowing down from the above literature review, this study aims to study the green initiative taken by the stakeholders of various government, aided and college with autonomous status, their awareness about and the challenges they faced for making their campus green.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand various initiatives taken by the institutions to make the campus green.
2. To know the awareness of green campus among the faculties of Government, Aided and Autonomous institutions of Calicut City
3. To find out the limiting factor that restricts the campus to go green

Hypothesis 1

H0: There is no significant difference among types of institution with respect to the awareness of the green concept.

H1: There is significant difference among types of institution with respect to the awareness of the green concept.

Hypothesis 2

H0: There is no significant association between the grade of institution and initiative taken to make the institution green

H1: There is significant association between the grade of institution and initiative taken to make the institution green

Hypothesis 3

H0: There is no significant difference among types of the institution with regard to the problems faced by them in implementing green campus initiatives.

H1: There is significant difference among type of the institution with regard to the problems faced by them in implementing green campus initiatives.

METHODOLOGY ADOPTED FOR THE STUDY

The researcher has adopted a simple random sampling method in probability sampling. The study was conducted by taking the faculties of Calicut district. A sample size of 80 teachers of various colleges were taken. Questionnaire was prepared and was administered to the respondents. Before finalizing the questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted administering 20 questionnaires to the respondents. Later after making appropriate editing, questionnaire was finalized.

THE INSTRUMENT

A self-constructed questionnaire was used as a research tool. It consisted of three main parts viz., demographic variables (gender, age, residence), to know whether the institution take any of these initiatives to make the campus green, dichotomous questions were provided and for understanding the awareness of the green concept and the limiting factor that restricts the campus to go green, 16 items with different possibilities of answering a 5-point Likert type items (Totally disagree – Slightly disagree – Neutral – Slightly agree – Totally agree) was included.

To check the reliability of the scale and the instrument used for data collection by working out Cronbach alpha which is a ratio very much similar to correlation coefficient, whose value should be more than 0.7 to judge a scale or questionnaire to be most reliable.

Table No.1

Table Reliability Statistics

Variables	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Awareness about green campus initiative	5	0.712
Problems in implementing green campus initiatives	11	0.844

Cronbach's Alpha values of all statements are found to be higher than 0.7, hence the internal consistencies of scaled variables are ensured.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table No.2

Profile of the Respondents

Characteristics	Variables	Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	40	53.3
	Female	35	46.7
Type of the College	Autonomous	11	14.7
	Government	36	48.0
	Aided	28	37.3
Age Group	Below 30	4	5.3
	31 – 40	31	41.3
	41 – 50	36	48
	Above 50	4	5.3
Experience	Below 5	10	13.3
	5 – 10	21	28
	10 -15	33	44
	Above 15	11	14.7
Grade of the College	A++	7	9.33
	A+	9	12
	A	15	20
	B++	25	33.33
	B+	19	25.34
Total		75	100%

(Source: Primary Data)

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Gender wise analysis shows that, out of the 75 respondents 53.3 per cent are male and 46.7 per cent are female. Profile of the respondents indicates that 14.7 per cent teachers from autonomous college, 48 per cent teachers from Government College and the remaining 37.3 per cent from aided colleges. Age group of the respondents reveals that large proportion of 48 per cent teachers belongs to the age group of 41 – 50 years. Second major age group is 31 – 40 years (41.3 per cent) and the respondents belong to the age group of below 30 and above 50 are 5.3 per cent each.

An analysis of the experience of the respondents shows that 44 per cent of them have experience of 10 – 15 years and 28 per cent are having the experience of 5 – 10 years. While teachers with experience of below 5 years is only 13.3 per cent and senior teachers with experience of above 15 years is 14.7 per cent. NAAC accreditation of the college shows that large proportion (33.33 per cent) of colleges are in the B++ grade and the second large category is B+ grade with 25.44 per cent. Colleges with A grade constitute 20 per cent of the sample and A+ grade colleges constitute 12 Per cent. Colleges with A++ grade is only 9.33 per cent of the total sample.

LEVEL OF AWARENESS ABOUT THE CONCEPT OF GREEN CAMPUS

Table No.3

Mean scores of level of awareness about the concept of green campus among different types of colleges with test of significance

Awareness about the concept		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	p value
Do you agree with the concept of Green Campus	Autonomous	11	4.64	.50	0.28	0.756
	Government	36	4.56	.65		
	Aided	28	4.46	.79		
Do you actively participate in green awareness programmes	Autonomous	11	3.82	1.17	0.63	0.533
	Government	36	3.53	1.11		
	Aided	28	3.36	1.22		
Do you want to organise and coordinate green awareness programmes	Autonomous	11	4.27	.65	1.26	0.291
	Government	36	3.78	1.15		
	Aided	28	3.64	1.22		
Do you think educational institutions have great role in creating green awareness	Autonomous	11	4.73	.65	0.87	0.423
	Government	36	4.58	.73		
	Aided	28	4.39	.88		
Do you recommend for grace mark to the students participating in green campus initiative	Autonomous	11	3.82	1.40	1.01	0.368
	Government	36	4.03	1.28		
	Aided	28	3.54	1.48		

(Source: Primary Data)

An analysis about the awareness of the concept of green campus shows that there is no significant difference among the autonomous, government and aided college teachers with regard to their level of awareness about the concept of green campus. The p values of the ANOVA test is higher than 0.05 in all cases. Hence, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference among type of institution with respect to the awareness of the green concept.

Analysis also reveals that all types of college teachers agree with the concept of green campus, active participation in green awareness programme, willingness to organize and co-ordinate green awareness programmes and think that educational institutions have great role in creating awareness about the green and also recommend grace mark for students participating in green campus initiative, as mean scores in all the cases are above three.

OPINION ABOUT THE GREEN CAMPUS INITIATIVES

The association between the colleges based on their NAAC accreditation status and green campus initiatives are evaluated by using chi square test. The analysis given in the Table No. 4, reveals that there is no significant association between the grade of the colleges and the initiatives taken like campus avoid plastic banners, campus or hostel have bio gas plant, campus provide compost bin for food waste and department conduct programmes to encourage green campus initiatives as the chi square values are higher than 0.05 in all the cases.

While there is significance association between the types of colleges based on their grade and green campus initiatives with regard to the aspects like campus is energy efficient, campus have poster to remind save water, water harvesting system, incinerators installed, took initiatives in planting native trees and having green student club as the p values of chi square test is less than 0.05 in all the cases.

Table No.4
Distribution of colleges on the basis of grade and opinion about green campus initiatives with test of significance

Green Campus Initiatives	Response	Grade of the College					Chi Square Value	Sig.
		A++	A+	A	B++	B+		
Campus is energy efficient	Yes	6	7	13	12	8	11.676	0.02*
	%	86	78	87	48	72		
	No	1	2	2	13	11		
	%	14	22	13	52	58		
Campus have poster to remind save water	Yes	6	8	12	10	8	14.059	0.007**
	%	86	89	80	40	72		
	No	1	1	3	15	11		
	%	14	11	20	60	58		
Campus have water harvesting system	Yes	7	7	11	11	7	11.985	0.017*
	%	100	78	73	44	36		
	No	0	2	4	14	12		
	%	0	22	27	56	63		
Incinerators installed	Yes	7	8	13	11	8	17.665	0.001**
	%	100	89	87	44	72		
	No	0	1	2	14	11		
	%	0	11	13	56	58		
Campus take initiative in planting native trees	Yes	5	7	11	8	7	11.875	0.018*
	%	72	78	73	32	36		
	No	2	2	4	17	12		
	%	28	22	27	68	64		
Campus avoid plastic banners	Yes	7	8	13	18	16	3.895	0.42
	%	100	89	86	72	84		
	No	0	1	2	7	3		
	%	0	11	13	28	16		
Campus/Hostels have bio gas plant	Yes	4	2	8	6	7	5.779	0.216
	%	57	22	53	24	37		
	No	3	7	7	19	12		
	%	43	78	47	76	63		
Campus provide compost bin for food waste	Yes	7	8	12	18	11	6.482	0.166
	%	100	89	80	72	58		
	No	0	1	3	7	8		
	%	0	11	20	28	42		
Campus have green student club	Yes	6	6	12	9	6	14.413	0.006**
	%	86	67	80	18	32		
	No	1	3	3	16	13		
	%	14	33	20	64	68		
Dept. conduct programmes to encourage green campus initiatives	Yes	7	6	11	18	13	3.007	0.557
	%	100	67	73	72	68		
	No	0	3	4	7	6		
	%	0	33	27	28	32		

Problems in implementing Green Campus Initiatives

Table No.5
Mean scores about the problems faced by the different types of colleges in implementing green campus imitative with test of significance

Problems	Type of College	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
No proper idea regarding the use of green technology	Autonomous	11	2.55	1.29	6.608	0.002**
	Government	36	3.78	0.87		
	Aided	28	3.54	0.99		
Absence of proper training	Autonomous	11	2.82	1.54	3.940	0.024*
	Government	36	3.78	0.98		
	Aided	28	3.75	0.85		
Absence of expert trainers	Autonomous	11	3.09	1.22	3.871	0.025*
	Government	36	4.00	1.04		
	Aided	28	3.96	0.79		
Lack of facilities to implement green concept	Autonomous	11	3.18	0.98	5.281	0.007 **
	Government	36	4.14	0.80		
	Aided	28	3.96	0.88		
Lack of awareness about the sources of fund	Autonomous	11	3.09	1.04	2.340	0.104
	Government	36	3.81	0.86		
	Aided	28	3.57	1.07		
Lack of fund	Autonomous	11	3.00	1.00	3.204	0.046*
	Government	36	3.75	0.87		
	Aided	28	3.25	1.17		
Improperutilisation of funds	Autonomous	11	2.81	1.25	0.766	0.469
	Government	36	3.27	1.08		
	Aided	28	3.14	1.01		
Lapse of fund	Autonomous	11	2.64	1.03	5.858	0.004**
	Government	36	3.81	0.98		
	Aided	28	3.39	1.03		
Lack of awareness programme for the students	Autonomous	11	3.18	0.98	0.138	0.871
	Government	36	3.33	1.01		
	Aided	28	3.21	1.17		
Absence of voluntary participation from students	Autonomous	11	3.09	0.94	0.239	0.788
	Government	36	3.36	1.02		
	Aided	28	3.29	1.33		
Lack of co-operation from NSS and NCC	Autonomous	11	2.27	1.19	1.127	0.330
	Government	36	2.72	0.91		
	Aided	28	2.43	1.07		

(Source: Primary Data)

Analysis given in the above table makes it clear that there is a significant difference among different types of colleges with regard to the problems faced by them in implementing the green campus initiatives. Results of ANOVA shows that p value is less than 0.05 and hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that there is significant difference among types of the institution with regard to the problems faced by them in implementing green campus initiative is accepted.

Significant difference is found among autonomous, government and aided colleges with regard to the problems like no proper idea regarding the use of green technology, absence of proper training, lack of expert trainers, lack of facilities

to implement green technology, lack of fund and lapse of fund. Government colleges and aided colleges are more affected due to these problems than the autonomous colleges.

Analysis also reveals that there is no significant difference among the autonomous, government and aided colleges with regard to lack of awareness about the sources of fund, lack of awareness programme for students, absence of voluntary participation from students and lack of support from NSS and NCC, as the p values of ANOVA test is higher than 0.05 in all these cases.

Conclusion

This paper examined the green campus initiatives and challenges in the government, aided and autonomous colleges in Kerala. Based on the observations made in the analysis it can be established that teachers in the all types of colleges are aware about the significance of green campus initiative and they are willing to organize and participate in green campus initiatives. As the teachers are aware of this concept, it becomes easy to implement the green initiative in the campuses. Apart from individual awareness, involvement of staff and students plays a very important role to create a green campus. Seminars, Green campus promotions, Campaigns, efforts to make paper less and plastic less campus etc., should be executed. Even developing green landscape in the campus will bring a sense of belongingness and acceptance among the stakeholders.

With regard to the implementation of the concept, it can be seen that government and aided colleges in Kerala are facing major problems like lack of fund, improper utilization of fund, lack of facilities and absence of expert trainers. But these problems are not affected by the autonomous colleges in Kerala. It can also be seen that NAAC grade of the college has also significant influence in the green campus initiatives, Colleges with higher grades have taken various measures to make the campus green and energy efficient as compared to the colleges with low grade. Hence, there should be an initiative on the part of the authorities to improve the green campus measures in the government and aided colleges with low NAAC grade.

Developing green campus is holistic which should aim to make environmental awareness and action an intrinsic part of the life. This initiative should include all stakeholders like students, teaching and non-teaching staff, local business people, visitors etc. Green Campus endeavors to extend learning beyond the classroom. This initiative will definitely reward long term commitment to continuous improvement from the campus community. This will also help in providing positive publicity for the campus by setting a good example in the community.

For developing green campus, there are two important attributes. First one can be considered as the physical environment, by reducing carbon footprints, energy efficiency, conserving water and managing waste effectively and the second aspect is social cultural aspect which will involve management, education, system, practices and relationship with local communities. It can be developed by organizing workshop on recycling activities, practical activities regarding conservation of energy, providing ideas on reuse, recycle and reduce. Thus development of green campus and its awareness will also spread to the local people which will have a greater impact on society.

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